

Subadult Virtual Anthropology Database (SVAD) Data Collection Protocol: Dental Morphological Traits on Virtual 3D Crania

G Richard Scott¹, Tatiana Vlemincq-Mendieta¹, Kyra E Stull^{1,2}, Elaine Y Chu¹, Kristen A Broehl¹, Christopher A Wolfe¹, M Kate Spradley³, Marin A Pilloud¹, Louise K Corron^{1*}

¹ Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Reno, United States; ² University of Pretoria, South Africa; ³ Texas State University, San Marcos, United States

*Corresponding author contact information:

Dr Louise Corron
Department of Anthropology
University of Nevada, Reno
1664 N Virginia St MS 0096
Reno, NV 89557 USA
lcorron@unr.edu

This document presents the standardized protocol developed to score dental morphological traits on 3D renderings of subadult crania obtained from computed tomography scans. This protocol was developed as part of National Institute of Justice Award 2019 DU-BX-0039. If the methodology presented herein is used or mentioned in a presentation or publication, then this document needs to be cited. Additionally, we strongly encourage all research using this protocol to be submitted to the Subadult Virtual Anthropology Database (SVAD) Zenodo Community to facilitate sharing and discovery of information (<https://zenodo.org/communities/svad/?page=1&size=20>).

Data

Crown and root traits will be recorded for all available permanent and deciduous dentition largely following the Arizona State University Dental Anthropology System (ASUDAS) outlined in Scott and Irish (2017) and Turner II et al. (1991). Modifications for deciduous teeth follow or are adapted from protocols outlined by Hanihara (1961) and Sciulli (1998).

- 16 crown traits and 5 root traits for permanent teeth
- 10 crown traits and 2 root traits for deciduous teeth

Dental morphological data are collected on all the left and right teeth. Most traits have already been dichotomized/trichotomized to increase reliability and to match rASUDAS (Scott et al., 2018). Therefore, the definitions per score will include the expanded/original grades from the previous references they were adapted from.

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Notes

Tooth Name Abbreviations

Per convention, abbreviations for each tooth are used: U = Upper (maxillary), L = Lower (mandibular), R = right, L = left, I = Incisor, C = Canine, P = Premolar, M = Molar. The number refers to tooth position. Upper-case letters denote permanent teeth and lower-case letters denote deciduous teeth. For example, URP3 is the permanent upper right third premolar and lli2 would indicate the deciduous lower left second (lateral) incisor. Importantly, we do not identify deciduous molars; the postcanine deciduous teeth are ontogenetically premolars and the evolutionary numbering of third and fourth is employed throughout for premolars.

Scoring Missing Data (NA/-1)

Score NA when the tooth is missing, or still erupting/developing/resorbing. Score -1 when the tooth is present and the trait could be scored but is not scored because the trait cannot be viewed in its entirety (*i.e.*, image quality, trauma, medical devices, shut mouth) or if you do not feel confident with a score.

The Effects of Dental or Orthodontic Procedures

When scoring traits like winging, crowding, diastema, and congenital absence ensure no dental procedures had taken place (*e.g.*, missing all P3s/P4s/M3s because of extraction or the presence of wires or a dental appliance). In these cases, score -1. When crown replacement or fillings are present, some or all occlusal traits may not be observable or scored; in these instances, a score of -1 is appropriate. If the provided Access database is used, the “**DataEntry**” form has a dedicated “**Comments**” cell for adding any notes during data collection.

Color-coded Nomenclature

- Blue: minimum developmental and/or eruption stage following AlQahtani et al. (2010) needed to score the trait
- Green: information about measurements
- Orange: important information to be aware of before scoring the trait

Scoring Terminology

The term score and grade are used interchangeably throughout the document. Therefore, a score of 0 is the same as a grade 0.

Suggestions/Guidance with Data Collection

- If you are debating between presence and absence (0 vs. 1), err on the side of absence (0) or score a -1 if you are uncomfortable deciding.
- Start with a 900 HU for permanent teeth and 600 HU for deciduous teeth for volume rendering. You can adjust the threshold, but do not go past +/- 200 HU for each type of tooth. The only exception is when scoring the seven root traits; the threshold can be increased beyond these limits to remove mandibular or maxillary bone to get a better view of the root structures.
- The left and right dental arcades are included in data collection. However, the tooth with the higher trait expression is typically used in data analysis.

Permanent Dental Traits

Dental Trait	Label	Observed Teeth
Winging	WING	Upper central incisors (UI1)
Diastema	DIAS	Upper central incisors and upper and lower canines (UI1, UC, LC)
Shoveling	SHOV	Upper incisors (UI1, UI2)
<i>Tuberculum dentale</i>	TD	Upper canines (UC)
Canine distal accessory ridge	DAR	Upper and lower canines (UC, LC)
Odontome	ODONT	All premolars (UP3, UP4, LP3, LP4)
Dental crowding	CROWD	First and second incisors as one unit; canine, third and fourth premolars as another unit (for upper and lower and both sides)
Hypocone	HYP	Upper molars (UM1, UM2, UM3)
Cusp 5 (metaconule)	C5	Upper molars (UM1, UM2, UM3)
Carabelli's trait	CARA	Upper molars (UM1, UM2, UM3)
Pegged/reduced/missing third molars	PRM	Upper and lower third molars (UM3, LM3)
Upper premolar root number	UPRT	Upper premolars (UP3, UP4)
Upper molar root number	UMRT	Upper molars (UM1, UM2, UM3)
Lower premolar multiple lingual cusps	PCN	Lower premolars (LP3, LP4)
Lower molar cusp number	LMCN	Lower molars (LM1, LM2, LM3)
Cusp 6 (entoconulid or <i>tuberculum sextum</i>)	C6	Lower molars (LM1, LM2, LM3)
Cusp 7 (metaconulid or <i>tuberculum intermedium</i>)	C7	Lower molars (LM1, LM2, LM3)
Protostylid	PROT	Lower molars (LM1, LM2, LM3)
Lower canine root number	LCRT	Lower canines (LC)
Tomes' root	TOM	Lower third premolars (LP3)
Lower molar root number	LMRT	Lower molars (LM1, LM2, LM3)

Winging (UI1) – WING

Patterned mesiolingual rotation of the upper central incisors (Scott and Irish, 2017) (Fig. 1). If the trait is present, use the measuring tool in Amira™ to establish the grade (see the “**Data Collection in Amira™**” section of the protocol).

- **Developmental stage:** the upper central incisors must be fully erupted (position 4 in AlQahtani et al. 2010) to score this trait.
- **Measurement:** use the angle option and take your measurement on the incisal edge, from one distal corner to the point of union of the mesial corners, to the other distal corner of the upper central incisors. Make sure to orient the incisors in an occlusal view. The angle you are measuring is on the labial side of the teeth.
- **To know before scoring:** if there is clear evidence of dental work do not score winging (-1). Both central incisors are needed to score this trait.

Scoring

Trait grades correspond to the angle formed at the point of union of the mesial corners of the incisal edges to the distal corners of the upper central incisors. The measurement is done on the labial surface of the teeth.

0. *Absence* (grade 0 from Scott and Irish, 2017): if the angle is equal or superior to 180° when viewed occlusally, winging is absent. Because winging is only present if it is observed bilaterally, this grade also includes unilateral winging and counter-winging (the rotation of the incisors is distolingual instead of mesiolingual).

1. *Presence* (grades 1-3 from Scott and Irish, 2017): if the angle is inferior to 180° when viewed occlusally, winging is present.

Fig. 1: Occlusal view of the upper central incisors illustrating the grades of winging on CT scans (the angles were drawn in Amira™).

Diastema (UI1, UC, LC) – DIAS

Any gap between the teeth with a separation of 0.5 mm or more. Diastemata can be scored in three locations: 1) maxillary central incisors, 2) maxillary canines, and 3) mandibular canines. Among the canines, the separation can occur on either side, between the canine and the lateral incisor, or the canine and the third premolar (Fig. 2). The current scoring system does not differentiate between the two locations (Pilloud, 2018). If the trait is present, use the measuring tool in Amira™ to establish the grade (see the “Data Collection in Amira™” section of the protocol).

- **Developmental stage:** all permanent teeth except M3 must be fully erupted to score this trait.
- **Measurement:** the gap that is observed and measured is located between the most mesial/distal points of the mesial/distal borders of the teeth.
- **To know before scoring:** score as -1 if teeth traditionally removed by dentists are missing on both sides (i.e., P3/P4 and M3). Also, to affirm the score, the Orthoslice view can be used to assess presence or absence of a gap between the crowns.

Scoring (grades from Pilloud, 2018)

- 0. *Absent:* < 0.50 mm space.
- 1. *Low-grade diastema:* 0.5-1.49 mm space.
- 2. *High-grade diastema:* ≥1.5 mm space.

	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2
UI1			
UC			
LC			

Fig. 2: Grades of diastemata for CT scans (measurements done in Amira™). First row: labial view of upper central incisors; second row: labial view of the right side of the upper dentition; third row: labial view of the left side of the lower dentition (grades 0 and 1) and labial view of right side of lower dentition (grade 2).

Shoveling (UI1, UI2) – SHO

Part of the marginal ridge complex of the anterior teeth (Figs. 3a and 3b). It involves the development of mesial and distal marginal ridges on the lingual surface (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- [Developmental stage](#): the entire crown needs to be developed (stage Crc, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. Note, the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.

Scoring

UI1 ranked scale

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): smooth lingual surface of the crown with no marginal ridges, or very slight expression with the mesial marginal ridge not extending to the basal eminence.

1. *Moderate* (grades 2-3 from Scott and Irish, 2017): ridges more pronounced, extending at least halfway down the crown, and sometimes almost coalescing at the basal eminence. To score as grade 1, the trait must be clearly present.

2. *Pronounced* (grades 4-7 from Scott and Irish, 2017): well-developed ridges usually converging at the basal eminence. If they almost converge and there is a deep fossa, it is also a grade 2. In higher expression, the ridges might be folding around on themselves at the basal eminence.

UI2 ranked scale:

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): smooth lingual surface of the crown with no marginal ridges, or faint mesial and distal marginal ridges. Sometimes a shallow fossa might be visible without apparent marginal ridges.

1. *Moderate* (grades 2-3 from Scott and Irish, 2017): moderate marginal ridges with little to moderate fossa formation. To score grade 1, the trait must be clearly visible.

2. *Pronounced* (grades 4-7 from Scott and Irish, 2017): well-developed marginal ridges that come in contact at the lingual base of the crown, forming a distinct lingual fossa. Sometimes, the expression is so pronounced that the ridges contact at almost the incisal surface of the basal eminence, assuming a barrel shape.

	UI1 shoveling	UI2 shoveling
Grade 0		
Grade 1		
Grade 2		

Fig. 3a: Grades of UI1 (left column) and UI2 (right column) shoveling for CT scans. Lingual views. All UI2 are from the right side of the dental arcade.

Fig. 3b: Example of ULI2 barrel-shape. Graded as 2. Left is an occlusal view; right is a lingual view.

Tuberculum dentale (UC) - TD

Cingular projections on the lingual surface of the upper anterior teeth; although, this is only scored here on the upper canine (Fig. 4). They typically take the form of ridges and/or tubercles (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- [Developmental stage](#): the entire crown needs to be developed (stage Crc, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): no tubercle formation.

1. *Presence* (grades 2-7 from Scott and Irish, 2017): clear tubercle defined by two grooves, one on each side.

Fig. 4: Grades of UC tuberculum dentale for CT scans. Lingual view with the mesial border on the left.

Canine distal accessory ridge (UC, LC) – DAR

The lingual lobe segment of the upper and lower canines typically expresses a medially positioned essential ridge, a mesial marginal ridge, and a distal marginal ridge. The mesial marginal ridge is primarily vertical in orientation and often extends almost to the level of the cusp tip. The distal marginal ridge is shorter and courses away at an angle from the essential ridge. Between the essential ridge and distal marginal ridge, an additional ridge can manifest on the lingual aspect of the distal lobe segment, hence the name distal accessory ridge (DAR) (Fig. 5). The ridge is more common and pronounced on the upper canine (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- Developmental stage: the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).
- To know before scoring: unfortunately, when in the crypt, the distal border is often against P3, which obscures the scoring.

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017).

1. *Presence* (grades 2-5 from Scott and Irish, 2017).

Fig. 5: Grades of DAR for CT scans (UC = Upper Canine; LC = Lower Canine). All images present the lingual view with the mesial border on the left.

Odontome (UP3, UP4, LP3, LP4) - ODONT

Odontomes are expressed in the central sulcus of premolars. Typically, they are conical in shape and readily scored in unworn or slightly worn dentitions (Scott and Irish, 2017). This is a fairly rare trait; therefore, no example from the study sample was found to illustrate it here.

- [Developmental stage: the crown needs to be \$\frac{3}{4}\$ developed \(stage Cr \$\frac{3}{4}\$, AlQahtani et al., 2010\) to be scored \(the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt\).](#)

Scoring (grades from Scott and Irish, 2017)

0. *Absence.*
1. *Presence.*

Dental crowding (I1 and I2; C, P3 and P4) - CROWD

Defined as the presence of any tooth that deviates from ideal alignment through either rotation or displacement. Rotation and displacement can be categorized into two types: major or minor. Minor rotation is under 45°, where major rotation is defined as approximately 45° or greater from ideal alignment. Minor displacement is under approximately 1.5 mm, and major displacement is approximately 1.5 mm or greater from ideal alignment either labially or lingually.

Crowding is subdivided into incisal (first and second incisors) and lateral (canine and premolars) (Pilloud, 2018). To score this trait, look at the alignment/misalignment of the tooth you are scoring (e.g., ULI1) compared to the entire dental arcade. If the tooth is misaligned with the rest of the arcade, crowding is present and if the tooth is aligned with the rest of the arcade, crowding is absent (Fig. 6).

- [Developmental stage: all permanent teeth except M3 must be fully erupted to score this trait.](#)
- [To know before scoring: do not score incisal crowding if winging is present \(-1\). Remember, mandibular winging is not scored here but it exists. Do not score if one of the teeth \(i.e., I1, I2, C, P3, or P4\) is missing, or if any evidence of dental work is present \(-1\).](#)

Scoring

Incisal (first and second incisor from same side):

0. *Absent or slight* (grades 0-1 from Pilloud, 2018): both teeth are either in ideal alignment with the rest of the arcade, or one or both teeth show minor rotation and/or displacement.
1. *Moderate or severe* (grades 2-3 from Pilloud, 2018): at least one tooth shows major rotation and/or displacement compared to the rest of the dental arcade.

Lateral (canine and third and fourth premolars from same side):

0. *Absent or slight* (grades 0-1 from Pilloud, 2018): all three teeth are in ideal alignment with the rest of the arcade or one or more teeth show minor rotation and/or displacement.
1. *Moderate or severe* (grades 2-3 from Pilloud, 2018): at least one tooth shows major rotation and/or displacement compared to the rest of the dental arcade.

	Grade 0		Grade 1	
Upper incisal (UI1 and UI2)				
Lower incisal (LI1, LI2)				
Upper lateral (UC, UP3, UP4)				
Lower lateral (LC, LP3, LP4)				

Fig. 6: Grades of dental crowding for CT scans. First row: occlusal view of upper right incisors; second row: occlusal view of lower left incisors; third row: occlusal view of upper right canine and premolars; fourth row: Occlusal view of lower left canine and premolars.

Hypocone (UM1, UM2, UM3) - HYP

Cusp that is attached to the distolingual surface of the trigon (Fig. 7). In terms of morphology, the variation takes the form of hypocone reduction or loss. The hypocone is almost invariably present on the first molar, retaining its ancestral four-cusped form in most individuals. The second molar varies much more than the first molar but much less than the third molar (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- Developmental stage: the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).
- To know before scoring: this trait must be scored in an occlusal view.

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): no hypocone expression of any form; a true three-cusped tooth. Sometimes, a low-level expression of the hypocone is present, seen more like an outline on the distolingual aspect of the trigon. As G. Richard Scott would say, the hypocone seems to be painted on the smooth surface of the protocone.

1. *Small cusp or tubercle* (grades 2-3 from Scott and Irish, 2017): cusp/tubercle with a free apex assuming a conical or ovate shape. To score a grade 1, the trait must be clearly visible.

2. *Well-developed cusp* (grades 4-6 from Scott and Irish, 2017): cusp comparable in size to the rest of the cusps from the trigon.

	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2
UM1	No known example		
UM2			
UM3			

Fig. 7: Grades of the hypocone for CT scans (UM1 = Upper First Molar; UM2 = Upper Second Molar; UM3 = Upper Third Molar). Occlusal view with buccal side on the left.

Cusp 5 (metaconule) (UM1, UM2, UM3) – C5

Cusp 5 takes the form of a conule that is expressed between the hypocone and metacone of the upper molars (Fig. 8). This variant does not attain the size of other accessory cusps (*e.g.*, cusp 6, cusp 7) so the range in expression goes from a small conule to a moderate or medium-sized cusp (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- Developmental stage: the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. The tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.

Scoring

0. *Absent* (grade 0 from Scott and Irish, 2017): only one vertical groove on distal surface of upper molar between hypocone and metacone.

1. *Present* (grades 1-5 from Scott and Irish, 2017): expression can range from a slight conule to a medium cusp.

	Grade 0	Grade 1
UM1		No known example
UM2		
UM3		

Fig. 8: Grades of cusp 5 for CT scans (UM1 = Upper First Molar; UM2 = Upper Second Molar; UM3 = Upper Third Molar). Occlusal view with buccal side on the left.

Carabelli's trait (UM1, UM2, UM3) – CARA

Carabelli's trait is a cingular derivative expressed on the lingual surface of the protocone (Fig. 9). It shows a wide range of expression, from complete absence to a large free-standing tubercle that approximates the hypocone in size (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. The tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.
- **To know before scoring:** to score 1, the trait has to be clearly present. To score 2, the trait has to clearly present with a free apex. If the free apex is difficult to see, use the examples below and base your assessment on the size of the trait.

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): the protocone does not exhibit pits or cusps on its lingual surface. Sometimes a vertical groove separates the protocone from the mesial ridge complex; when this occurs, a slight eminence deflects distally from that groove.

1. *Present with no free apex* (grades 2-4 from Scott and Irish, 2017): to score grade 1, the trait must be clearly visible. This score may present as a pit, slight elevation marked by two vertical grooves, or a tubercle with no free apex (typical bird-wing form).

2. *Tubercle with free apex* (grades 5-7 from Scott and Irish, 2017), usually called Carabelli's cusp.

		Grade 0	Grade 1			Grade 2	
UM1	Occlusal view						
	Lingual view						
UM2	Occlusal view						
	Lingual view						
UM3	Occlusal view						
	Lingual view						

Fig. 9: Grades of Carabelli's trait for CT scans (UM1 = Upper First Molar; UM2 = Upper Second Molar; UM3 = Upper Third Molar). Occlusal view with buccal side on the left; lingual view with mesial side on the right. Note: more examples of grades 1 and 2 have been provided for UM1 because the trait has shown more variability in that tooth than in the other two.

Pegged/Reduced/Missing third molar (UM3, LM3) – PRM

As loss and reduction are elements of the same phenomenon, third molars have a single trait that involves pegged or reduced forms as well as congenital absence (Scott and Irish, 2017) (Fig. 10).

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. The tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.
 - o For congenital absence: tooth development needs to be at least 3 years over the maximum age limit for development according to the AlQahtani et al. (2010) developmental atlas. This means that if M2 has reached R $\frac{1}{2}$, with the root at the same height as the crown, and M3 is still not in its crypt, it can be considered congenitally absent. Asymmetry between left and right teeth can occur, with one side present (grades 0 to 2) and the other absent (grade 3).
- **To know before scoring:** when a reduced or peg-shaped M3 is present, it can be difficult to estimate the developmental stage since the scale has been reduced. In that case, if the crown is developed enough that you feel certain it is one or the other, it can be scored.
 - o Molars can be surgically removed. Make sure there are no indications of such procedures.
 - o If M3 is reduced or peg-shaped, do not score the rest of traits on that tooth (NA).

Scoring (grades from Scott and Irish, 2017)

0. *Normal:* third molar present and normal.

1. *Reduced:* third molar significantly reduced in size (approximately $\frac{1}{2}$ normal size, with two or more cusps).

2. *Peg-shaped:* third molar peg-shaped; only a single cusp evident.

3. *Missing:* third molar congenitally absent.

	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
UM3				
LM3				

Fig. 10: Grades of PRM for CT scans (UM3 = Upper Third Molar; LM3 = Lower Third Molar). Occlusal view with the buccal side on the right.

Upper premolar root number (UP3, UP4) – UPRT

Upper premolars have either one, two, or three root cones (Fig. 11). Typically, there are two. One cone is buccal (below buccal cusp), and one is lingual (below lingual cusp). The root cones may or may not be separated by an inter-radicular projection (*i.e.*, root bifurcation). When there is no separation and you can only observe a vertical groove that separates the buccal and lingual root cones, the tooth is one-rooted. If there is a bifurcation that extends from at least $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ of total root length, the tooth is two-rooted. Very rarely, there are two buccal roots. When these are bifurcated along with a bifurcation of the lingual root, the result is a three-rooted upper premolar. Although UP3 is the key tooth for upper premolar root number, UP4 is occasionally two-rooted, but this is much less common than a two-rooted UP3 (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- [Developmental stage](#): the root needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored.
- [To know before scoring](#): be careful when scoring this trait to not confuse root bifurcation with an open apex. Check your volume rendering, if too much cementum has been removed, the root canal gets exposed giving a false impression of root bifurcation.

Scoring (grades from Scott and Irish, 2017):

1. *One-rooted upper premolar*: root grooves separate cones but no inter-radicular projection.
2. *Two-rooted upper premolar*: inter-radicular projection separates buccal and lingual root cones for at least $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ of total root length.
3. *Three-rooted upper premolar*: an inter-radicular projection separates the buccal root into two distinct roots, and another projection separating the two buccal roots from a single lingual root).

		Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
UP3	Buccal view			
	Apical view			
UP4	Buccal view			
	Apical view			

Fig. 11: Root number of upper premolars for CT scans (UP3 = Upper Third Premolar; UP4 = Upper Fourth Premolar). Buccal view with mesial side on the right; apical view with buccal side on the left. Note: the second example of UP3 grade 0 shows a one-rooted tooth with a bifurcation of less than $\frac{1}{4}$ of the total root length.

Upper molar root number (UM1, UM2, UM3) – UMRT

This trait is the number of roots each available upper molar exhibits (Figs. 12a and 12b). In modern human populations, most UM1s still have three primary roots. Because of space limitations, it is quite common for UM3 to exhibit three root cones but with no inter-radicular projections separating them. For that reason, UM3 often has one root. The tooth between the highly conserved UM1 and highly variable UM3 is the second molar. This tooth can exhibit either three roots like UM1 or several types of root cone fusion, producing either a one-rooted or a two-rooted UM2. Independent roots must show a bifurcation of at least $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ of total root length (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- [Developmental stage](#): the root needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored.
- [To know before scoring](#): be careful when scoring this trait to not confuse root bifurcation with an open apex. Check your volume rendering as well, if too much cementum has been removed, the root canal gets exposed giving an impression of root bifurcation. Sometimes just the apices of the roots are fused, with the rest of the roots being unfused. In these cases, score the roots as unfused.

Scoring

1. *One-rooted upper molar*: root cones are separated by grooves but there are no inter-radicular projections. If possible, note if all roots are fused (1a); if all roots are fused except the disto-buccal (DB) and lingual (L) roots (1b); if all roots are fused except the mesio-buccal (MB) and the lingual (L) roots (1c); or if all roots are fused except the mesio-buccal (MB) and disto-buccal (DB) roots (1d).

Fig. 12a: Cross-section drawings showing the possible root fusions resulting in one-rooted UM1.

2. *Two-rooted upper molar*: one inter-radicular projection separates one root from two fused roots. Note if possible if the fusion is of the two buccal roots (2a), of the mesio-buccal and lingual roots (2b), or of the disto-buccal and lingual roots (2c).

3. *Three-rooted upper molar*: three inter-radicular projections separate all three roots for at least $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ of total root length.

		Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
UM1	Buccal view	No known example		
	Apical view			
UM2	Buccal view			
	Apical view			
UM3	Buccal view			
	Apical view			

Fig. 12b: Grades of upper molar root number for CT scans (UM1 = Upper First Molar; UM2 = Upper Second Molar; UM3 = Upper Third Molar). Buccal view with mesial side on the right; apical view with buccal side on the left.

Lower premolar multiple lingual cusps (LP3, LP4) – PCN

In contrast to the upper premolars, the lower premolars have lingual cusps that are always smaller than the buccal cusps (Fig. 13). Typically, the lingual cusp of the lower premolars has a mesial placement relative to the buccal cusp. When there are accessory cusps, they are usually smaller and distal to the larger mesial lingual cusp (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).
- **To know before scoring:** just the lingual cusps are counted, do not include the buccal cusp.

Scoring

0. *Lingual cusp has no free apex, or single lingual cusp* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017).

1. *Two or three lingual cusps* (grades 2-3 from Scott and Irish, 2017).

	Grade 0		Grade 1	
	0 cusps	1 cusp	2 cusps	3 cusps
LP3		No known example		
LP4	No known example			

Fig. 13: Grades of lower premolar lingual cusp number for CT scans. Occlusal view with mesial side on the left.

Lower molar cusp number (LM1, LM2, LM3) – LMCN

Number of cusps on lower molars (Figs 14a and 14b). Cusp 7 is not counted here to avoid confusion of cusp homologies (Turner et al., 1991).

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. The tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.
- **To know before scoring:**
 - o Be cognizant of crown replacement for all molar traits.
 - o To score grade 5, cusp 5 must be clearly visible.
 - o Molars with just three cusps are rare, and usually not seen in first molars.
 - o Do not score this trait if the molar is 2-cusped (happens rarely on LM3).
 - o If cusp 6 is present with no cusp 5, do not score the trait (NA).

Scoring

3. *Three cusps:* usually two mesial cusps and one distal cusp.

4. *Cusps 1-4 are present:* 1, protoconid; 2, metaconid; 3, hypoconid; 4, entoconid.

5. *More than 4 cusps:* cusp 5 or cusps 5 and 6 are present. Do not score this trait if just cusp 6 is present and not cusp 5 (cusp 5 is buccally located, linked to the hypoconid, while cusp 6 is lingually located, linked to the entoconid).

	Grade 3	Grade 4	Grade 5	
LM1	No known example			
LM2				
LM3				

Fig. 14a: Grades of lower molar cusp number for CT scans (LM1 = Lower First Molar; LM2 = Lower Second Molar; LM3 = Lower Third Molar). Occlusal view with buccal side on the right. Note: the left examples on Grade 5 column are 5-cusped molars, while the right examples are 6-cusped molars.

Fig. 14b: Example of a LRM2 with a cusp 6 and no cusp 5. Occlusal view with buccal side on the right.

Cusp 6 (entoconulid or tuberculum sextum) (LM1, LM2, LM3) – C6

Like the hypoconulid, cusp 6 is expressed on the distal portion of the lower molars (Fig. 15). While the hypoconulid is associated with the hypoconid (cusp 3), cusp 6 is associated with the entoconid (cusp 4), hence the term entoconulid (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

0. Absence of cusp 6 (grade 0 from Scott and Irish, 2017).
1. Presence of cusp 6 (grades 1-5 from Scott and Irish, 2017).

	Grade 0		Grade 1
LM1			
LM2			
LM3			

Fig. 15: Grades of lower molar cusp 6 for CT scans (LM1 = Lower First Molar; LM2 = Lower Second Molar; LM3 = Lower Third Molar). Occlusal view with the buccal side on the right. Note: the left examples on Grade 0 column are 4-cusped molars, while the right examples are 5-cusped molars.

Cusp 7 (metaconulid or tuberculum intermedium) (LM1, LM2, LM3) – C7

Cusp 7 is a wedge-shaped accessory cusp expressed between cusps 2 (metaconid) and 4 (entoconid); hence *tuberculum intermedium* (Scott and Irish, 2017) (Fig. 16).

- Developmental stage: the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. The tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.
- To know before scoring: do not confuse cusp 7 with the distal lobe of the metaconid.

Scoring

- 0. *Absent* (grade 0 from Scott and Irish, 2017): no accessory cusp between cusps 2 and 4.
- 1A. Defined by a groove on the lingual surface of the metaconid and *does not* assume the typical wedge-shaped form of a cusp 7 (grade 1A from Scott and Irish, 2017).
- 1. *Distinct cusp* (grades 1-4 from Scott and Irish, 2017 (excluding 1A)).

		Grade 0	Grade 1A	Grade 1
LM1	Occlusal view			
	Lingual view			
LM2	Occlusal view			
	Lingual view			
LM3	Occlusal view			
	Lingual view			

Fig. 16: Grades for lower molar cusp 7 for CT scans (LM1 = Lower First Molar; LM2 = Lower Second Molar; LM3 = Lower Third Molar). Occlusal view with buccal side on the left, lingual view with mesial side on the right.

Protostylid (LM1, LM2, LM3) – PROT

The protostylid is a cingular derivative (Fig. 17). In some regards it is a mirror image of the Carabelli's trait in that it is expressed on the mesiobuccal cusp of the lower molars rather than the mesiolingual cusp of the upper molars. Despite some parallels, the protostylid never attains the status of a pronounced Carabelli's trait in modern humans (Scott and Irish, 2017).

- [Developmental stage](#): the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored. The tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt.

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grade 0 from Scott and Irish, 2017): no positive expression on buccal surface of lower molar.

1. *Pit* (grade 1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): buccal pit of varying sizes, situated around the midpoint of the crown in the protoconid–hypoconid inter-lobe groove.

2. *Presence* (grades 2-7 from Scott and Irish): ranging in expression from slight swelling to a distinctive tubercle.

		Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2
LM1	Occlusal view			
	Buccal view			
LM2	Occlusal view			
	Buccal view			
LM3	Occlusal view			
	Buccal view			

Fig. 17: Grades of lower molar protostylid for CT scans (LM1 = Lower First Molar; LM2 = Lower Second Molar; LM3 = Lower Third Molar). Occlusal view with the buccal side on the left; buccal view with the mesial side on the left.

Lower canine root number (LC) – LCRT

In some instances, the lower canines exhibit two roots instead of the usual single root (Scott and Irish, 2017) (Fig. 18).

- Developmental stage: the root needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored.
- To know before scoring: be careful when scoring this trait to not confuse root bifurcation with an open apex. Check your volume rendering; if too much cementum has been removed, the root canal gets exposed giving an impression of root bifurcation.

Scoring (grades from Scott and Irish, 2017):

1. *One-rooted LC*: one root with or without root grooves separating buccal and lingual cones.
2. *Two-rooted LC*: two roots with inter-radicular projection separating buccal and lingual cones by at least $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ of total root length.

	Grade 1	Grade 2
Buccal view		
Apical view		

Fig. 18: Grades for LC root number for CT scans. Buccal view with mesial side on the right; apical view with buccal side on the left.

Tomes' root (LP3) – TOM

There are not clearly distinct buccal and lingual root cones, but a buccal root cone and one or more lingual cones, with the most prominent on the mesial boundary of the tooth. An LP3 may exhibit one, two, three, or four root radicals. There may, or may not be, inter-radicular projections separating these radicals. Tomes' root constitutes that instance where a mesiolingual root cone exhibits an inter-radicular projection, producing an independent root (Scott and Irish, 2017) (Fig. 19).

- **Developmental stage:** the root needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored.
- **To know before scoring:** be careful when scoring this trait to not confuse root bifurcation with an open apex. To score the trait on the scans: (1) use the sagittal cross-section of the orthoslice option, (2) get as close as possible to the *mesial* aspect of the LP3 root, (3) make sure the volume rendering shows the entirety of the root removing as much of the mandibular bone as possible, (4) score the trait.

Scoring

0. *Slight or no groove separating cones on mesial surface of LP3 root* (grades 0 -1 from Scott and Irish, 2017). If the groove is present but is not deep.

1. *Deep V-shaped groove separating cones, to at least $\frac{1}{3}$ of the root on the mesial surface* (grades 2-5 from Scott and Irish, 2017). The lingual cone can present an apex starting to free itself from the buccal root. This grade can present deep mesial and distal grooves, sometimes ending on a true two-rooted LP3. To score a grade 1, the trait must be clearly present.

Fig. 19: Grades of Tomes' root for CT scans. Lingual view with mesial side on the left.

Lower molar root number (LM1, LM2, LM3) - LMRT

Lower molars generally have two roots, a mesial root associated with the trigonid and a distal root associated with the talonid. As the most conservative tooth in the lower molar district, LM1 retains the ancestral two-rooted phenotype most of the time (Scott and Irish, 2017) (Fig. 20a).

- **Developmental stage:** the root needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored.
- **To know before scoring:**
 - o Be careful when scoring this trait to not confuse root bifurcation with an open apex. Check your volume rendering as well, if too much cementum has been removed, the root canal gets exposed giving an impression of root bifurcation.
 - o Do not confuse the root number trait with root supernumerary structures. Root number can just be one to three-rooted molar, and are located mesial and distal when two rooted, and when three-rooted, the third root is disto-lingually located. The root supernumerary structures are located between the mesial and distal roots (see Fig. 20b). These structures are not scored here.

Scoring

1. *One-rooted lower molar:* mesial and distal roots of lower molars can be fused on either buccal or lingual aspect or both. Note if possible if the fusion is on both sides (1a), on the buccal side (1b), or on the lingual side (1c). 1b and 1c must show a C-shaped root when looking from an apical view.
2. *Two-rooted lower molar:* inter-radicular structure produces clear separation of mesial and distal roots for at least $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{3}$ of total root length.
3. *Three-rooted lower molar:* the extra root must be disto-lingually located.

		Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
LM1	Buccal view			
	Apical view			
LM2	Buccal view			
	Apical view			
LM3	Buccal view			
	Apical view			

Fig. 20a: Grades of lower molar root number for CT scans (LM1 = Lower First Molar; LM2 = Lower Second Molar; LM3 = Lower Third Molar). Buccal view with mesial side on the right; apical view with buccal side on the left.

Fig. 20b: Example of a root supernumerary structure (located between the mesial and distal root on the lingual side, also known as radix entomolaris). This trait is not scored here.

Deciduous Dental Traits

Dental Trait	Label	Observed Teeth
Winging	wing	Upper central incisors (ui1)
Shoveling	shov	Upper incisors (ui1, ui2)
Hypocone	hyp	Upper fourth premolar (up4)
Cusp 5 (metaconule)	c5	Upper fourth premolar (up4)
Carabelli's trait	cara	Upper fourth premolar (up4)
Root sheath	rtsh	Upper premolars (up3, up4)
Delta form	delta	Lower third premolar (lp3)
Cusp number	cnlp	Lower fourth premolar (lp4)
Cusp 6 (<i>tuberculum sextum</i>)	c6	Lower fourth premolar (lp4)
Cusp 7 (<i>tuberculum intermedium</i>)	c7	Lower fourth premolars (lp4)
Protostylid	prot	Lower fourth premolar (lp4)
Root number	rn	All teeth

Winging (ui1) – wing

Variations in the alignment of the central incisors (Dahlberg, 1963) (Fig. 21).

- [Developmental stage](#): the upper central incisors must be fully erupted to score this trait.
- [To know before scoring](#): both central incisors are needed to score this trait.

Scoring (grades from Sciulli, 1998):

0. *Absent*: ui1's distal borders on straight line or one or both distal borders toward lingual.

Unilateral winging is also part of this grade.

1. *Bilateral winging*: both distal borders toward labial.

Fig. 21: Grades of winging for CT scans. Occlusal view.

Shoveling (ui1, ui2) – shov

Variations on the lingual surface of the anterior dentition, specifically the mesial and distal marginal ridges, the cingulum, and the surface between these elements (Fig. 22). Different scans and slightly different definitions are presented to score each tooth (Hanihara, 1961, 1963; Sciulli, 1998).

- [Developmental stage](#): the entire crown needs to be developed (stage Crc, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be scored (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

ui1 ranking scale:

0. *Absent* (grade 0 from Hanihara, 1963): smooth lingual surface; sometimes slight ridges can be seen, mostly distal one; no concavity between ridges and cingulum.

1. *Semi-shovel shape* (grade 1 from Hanihara, 1963): both ridges present a slight elevation, but they run just one-half down the crown height from the incisal edge; slight concavity.

2. *Shovel shape* (grades 2-3 from Hanihara 1963): moderate to pronounced ridges (easily seen); reach almost or completely the cingulum; distinct concavity.

ui2 ranking scale:

0. *Absent* (grade 0 from Hanihara, 1963): none or slight ridges, if present then the borders between them and the lingual surface are unclear; concavity indistinct.

1. *Semi-shovel shape* (grade 1 from Hanihara, 1963): slight ridges and concavity clearer, but the ridges do not run all the way from the incisal edge to the cingulum.

2. *Shovel shape* (grades 2-3 from Hanihara 1963): moderate to pronounced ridges and concavity well developed; ridges are thicker than in grades 0-1.

	ui1 shoveling	ui2 shoveling
Grade 0		
Grade 1		
Grade 2		

Fig. 22: Grades of ui1 (left column) and ui2 (right column) shoveling for CT scans. Teeth are on a lingual view. All ui2 are rights, the mesial border is on the right.

Hypocone (up4) – hyp

Attached to the distolingual surface of the trigon (Fig. 23). In terms of morphology, the variation takes the form of hypocone reduction or loss.

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be graded (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).
- **To know before scoring:** this trait must be scored in an occlusal view.

Scoring

0. *No hypocone expression of any form* (grades 0-1 from Scott and Irish, 2017): a true three-cusped tooth. Sometimes, a low-level expression of the hypocone is present, seen more like an outline on the distolingual aspect of the trigon.

1. *Small cusp or tubercle with free apex* (grades 2-3 from Scott and Irish, 2017): to score a grade 1, the trait must be clearly visible.

2. *Well-developed cusp* (grades 4-6 from Scott and Irish, 2017): comparable in size (from the occlusal view) to the rest of the cusps of the trigon.

Fig. 23: Grades of up4 hypocone for CT scans. Occlusal view, buccal side on the left.

Cusp 5 (metaconule) (up4) – c5

Accessory cusp located between the metacone and hypocone of up4 (Sciulli, 1998).

- **Developmental stage:** the crown needs to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to be graded (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring (grades from Sciulli, 1998):

0. *Absent.*

1. *Present.*

Carabelli's trait (up4) – cara

Elaborations of the mesiolingual surface of up4 (Hanihara, 1961; Grine 1986; Turner et al., 1991; Lease 2003) (Fig. 24).

- Developmental stage: $\frac{3}{4}$ of the crown needs to be developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score the trait (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grades 0-1 from Hanihara, 1961; grade b from Grine, 1986): the protocone does not exhibit pits or cusps on its lingual surface. Sometimes a vertical groove separates the protocone from the mesial ridge complex; when this occurs, a slight eminence deflects distally from that groove.

1. *Present with no free apex* (grades 2-4 from Hanihara, 1961; grades a, c, d, and e from Grine, 1986): pit, or slight elevation marked by two vertical grooves, or tubercle with no free apex (typical bird-wing form). To score a grade 1, the trait must be clearly visible.

2. *Tubercle with free apex*, usually called Carabelli's cusp (grades 5-7 from Hanihara, 1961; grade f from Grine, 1986).

	Grade 0	Grade 1		Grade 2	
Occlusal view					
Lingual view					

Fig. 24: Scoring system used here to score Carabelli's trait in up4. Occlusal view: buccal side on left. Lingual view: mesial on the right.

Root sheath (up3, up4) - rtsh

A thin sheet of cementum may connect the distobuccal and lingual roots of the upper premolars (Jorgensen, 1956; Sciulli, 1998) (Fig. 25).

- **Developmental stage:** can be noted prior to root completion if the root is at least $\frac{3}{4}$ formed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010). Do not score this trait if one of the roots has been resorbed to a size smaller than the crown height (NA).
- **To know before scoring:** if present, the tooth is usually two-rooted. Be aware that it might be difficult to score this trait when the permanent premolar is located just under the tooth. If too difficult score as -1.

Scoring (grades from Sciulli, 1998):

0. Absent.

1. Present.

		Grade 0	Grade 1
up3	Lingual view		
	Apical view	The presence of the permanent premolar did not allow a readable apical view	
up4	Lingual view		
	Apical view		

Fig. 25: Grades of upper premolar root sheath for CT scans (up3 = upper third premolar; up4 = upper fourth premolar). Lingual view with mesial side on the left. Apical view with buccal side on the left.

Delta form (lp3) - delta

The delta form is present when the occlusal surface of lp3 forms a triangle with the base on the posterior of the tooth and the apex at the anterior (Dahlberg, 1951; Grine, 1986) (Fig. 26). The trait can be accompanied by a ridge extending from the distal marginal ridge into the talonid basin (Sciulli, 1998).

- Developmental stage: $\frac{3}{4}$ of the crown needs to be developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score the trait (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring (grades from Sciulli, 1998):

0. *Absent.*

1. *Present.*

Fig. 26: Grades of lp3 delta form for CT scans. Occlusal view with the buccal side on the right.

Cusp number (lp4) – cnlp

Enumeration of the cusps present on lp4 (Lease, 2003) (Fig. 27). For a cusp to be present, it has to show a distinct apical entity and be demarcated from adjacent cusps by fissures (Grine, 1986).

- Developmental stage: $\frac{3}{4}$ of the crown needs to be developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score the trait (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring (grades from Grine, 1986)

4. *Cusps 1-4* (1, protoconid; 2, metaconid; 3, hypoconid; 4, entoconid) are present.
5. *More than 4 cusps* (just cusp 5 or cusps 5 and 6 present). Do not score this trait if just cusp 6 is present and not cusp 5 (cusp 5 is buccally located, linked to the hypoconid, while cusp 6 is lingually located, linked to the entoconid).

Fig. 27: Grades for lp4 cusp number for CT scans. Occlusal view with buccal side on the right. Note: the examples for grade 5 goes from left to right: (1) unsure if 5 or 6 cusps, (2) clear 5-cusped, and (3) clear 6-cusped.

Cusp 6 (tuberculum sextum) (lp4) – c6

The development of an accessory cusp (c6) located between the hypoconulid (c5) and entoconid (Turner et al., 1991; Sciulli 1998) (Fig. 28).

- [Developmental stage](#): note that $\frac{3}{4}$ of the crown needs to be developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score the trait (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

0. *Absence* (grade 0 from Turner et al., 1991).
1. *Presence* (grades 1-5 from Turner et al., 1991).

Fig. 28: Grades for lp4 cusp 6 for CT scans. Occlusal view with buccal side on the right. Note: left example of grade 0 is a 4-cusped premolar; right example of grade 0 is a 5-cusped premolar.

Cusp 7 (tuberculum intermedium) (lp4) – c7

Development of an accessory cusp (c7) located between the metaconid and entoconid (Hanihara, 1961; Lease, 2003).

- [Developmental stage](#): $\frac{3}{4}$ of the crown needs to be developed (stage Cr $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score the trait (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

0. *No accessory cusp between cusps 2 and 4* (grade 0 from Hanihara, 1961).
- 1A. This expression does not assume the typical wedge-shaped form of a cusp 7 but is marked by a groove on the lingual surface of the metaconid (grade 1A from Turner et al., 1991).
1. *Distinct cusp* (grades 1-3 from Hanihara, 1961).

Protostylid (lp4) – prot

An elevation or ridge of enamel on the anterior part of the buccal surface of the lower premolars, which ascends from the gingival end of the buccal groove and extends mesio-occlusally (Grine, 1986) (Fig. 29).

- Developmental stage: ¾ of the crown needs to be developed (stage Cr ¾, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score the trait (the tooth can be scored even if still in its crypt).

Scoring

0. *Absence* of any expression (grade 0 from Hanihara, 1961; grades a and b from Grine’s 1986 mesiobuccal groove).

1. *Pit* (grade 1 from Hanihara, 1961; grade c from Grine’s 1986 mesio-buccal groove): buccal pit (a pit of varying sizes, situated around the midpoint of the crown in the protoconid–hypoconid inter-lobal groove).

2. *Presence* (grades 2-6 from Hanihara, 1961; grades a, b, and c from Grine’s 1986 protostylid): from slight swelling to a distinctive tubercle.

	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2
Occlusal view			
Buccal view			

Fig. 29: Scoring system used here to score the protostylid on lp4 from CT scans. Occlusal view: buccal side on the left. Buccal view: mesial side on the left.

Root number (all teeth) – rn

The number of roots is counted for each tooth in individuals whose roots are completed (apices can remain open). For anterior tooth roots to be counted as double, separation between the roots must have extended for at least $\frac{1}{4}$ of the distance from the apical end (Sciulli, 1998).

- Developmental stage: root has to be $\frac{3}{4}$ developed (stage R $\frac{3}{4}$, AlQahtani et al., 2010) to score this trait.
- To know before scoring: attention must be paid to root resorption (score as NA if the root length is shorter than the crown height). Also, due to root resorption the tooth might seem to have an extra root. Sometimes, the quality of the scan does not allow the observer to visualize the roots separately from the alveolar bone; in these occasions it might seem like an extra root as well. Be aware that if root sheath is present, up3 and up4 would have two roots.

Scoring (grades from Sciulli, 1998):

1. *One root.*
2. *Two roots.*
3. *Three roots.*
4. *Four roots.*

Data collection in Amira™

1. Opening Amira™

Click on the “**Project**” tab to open a workspace. Before selecting anything else, click the perspective button. The button is located in a bar of other buttons just above the viewing panes and looks like an eye: . Use the parallel line setting for all specimen editing and measuring. **You have to reset this every time you reopen Amira™.**

Choose [*Open Data...*] (green button in the “**Project View**” pane in the upper left corner).

2. Loading a stack of CT scans

Find the individual you are interested in and select all of the DICOMs in that folder (NB: not the DICOM directory). **Click [Open]**. Always select the folder that has “ST” in the name. This stands for “Soft Tissue” and has a better resolution than “Bone”. You can choose folders with names including “Head, Head-Neck”, or “Whole Body” as they all include the upper body and skull.

If you get a warning about the file size being too large, choose the radio button for “Load complete volume into memory” and **click [OK]**.

A dialog box called “DICOM Loader” will prompt you to check the parameters of the DICOM stack. Scroll through the window and if everything looks good (not out of order numbering, gaps in the data, etc.), **click [OK]**. Any errors will be shown as red numbers in the list of DICOMs. If that is the case, only select the DICOM files that appear in black by pressing shift and clicking on the first and last DICOM of the stack that you want to open.

3. Visualizing the CT slices

The file appears as a green lozenge in the “**Project View**” pane. Select the orange [**Orthoslice**] tab in the “**Project View**” pane. The CT slice should appear in the viewing console on the right. You can change the plane of the slice view by selecting xy, xz, or yz in the console header. If the hand is selected in that header, you can use it to move the exam around. You can also scroll through the slices by clicking the **box next to the Slice Number line** in the “Properties” pane and using the mouse to scroll or moving the cursor between the two triangles.

4. Creating a Volume Rendering of the Skull and teeth

Select the green lozenge. Click on the yellow [**Volume Rendering**] lozenge. The soft tissue of the scanned body should appear in the viewing console on the right. You can use the mouse on hand mode to turn the body around at different angles.

In the “**Properties**” pane, move the left cursor of the “**Colormap**” higher to adjust the masking value (the number on the left). This allows you to hide soft tissue and only visualize bones or teeth, the further you adjust the value. Higher values will only allow to visualize the densest elements (metal, teeth, etc.). You can also type a value in that left box and lower the right slider

as well. If you cannot see the teeth, you can move the body around and/or unselect the orange square in the [Orthoslice] lozenge to hide the contents of the CT slice. A good range of values should encompass part of the grey peaks you can see in the “Colormap”.

To adjust the transparency, in the “Properties” pane, click on the [Edit box] of the Colormap line. You can scroll down the menu and choose one of the colormap options. You can always revert back to the original setting if necessary by selecting it in the “Edit” box at any point.

5. Scoring traits

Once you are happy with the way the teeth look (not too transparent, roots complete, visible morphological structures...), you can start observing and scoring traits. Don't forget that you can move the reconstruction around by clicking it with the hand option selected.

Fill in the database with the scores for the traits you can observe. If you can't score a trait because the view is obstructed (trauma, missing anatomical region, image quality), please put -1 as a score.

Taking measurements in Amira™ (linear and angular)

Amira™'s measuring tool will be used to score the following three traits: reduced M3, diastema and winging.

- At the top of the Viewing panel, click on the ruler icon to open up the measuring tool. You can select either “Line” or “Angle”. A yellow [Measurement] lozenge should appear in “Project View”.
- Click on it and select [Measurement] in the “Properties” pane below. You can choose a linear measurement (for diastema and reduced M3) by selecting the ruler icon or an angle (for dental winging) by selecting the angle icon.
- Go to the “Viewing” pane, where your mouse should be an arrow with a small “M” next to it, showing you the tool is active, and click on the location where you would place the first point of your measurement then click on the location where you would place the second point. For angles, you will need to place three points in the same way.
- You can modify your measurement/angle by making sure the [Measurement] lozenge is selected and the mouse has the “M” next to it (the points will appear as spheres) and clicking on the point you want to move, then on the location you want to move your point to.

Comments

If you need to hide some parts of the body to facilitate scoring (like lower jaw, half of the skull, upper teeth, vertebrae, ribs, etc.), *select the orange Orthoslice* lozenge. In the “Properties” pane, click on the icon that looks like a cube with a green line crossing it (**the Clip tool**). Click on it once to hide half of the body, click on it again to see the full body and click on it a third time to see the other half of the body. You can do this in every plane, by changing the plane from xy to xz and yz in the “Orientation” line and in the viewing console while the [Orthoslice] lozenge is selected and by keeping that Clip tool selected. This will hide whatever structures are in front or behind the slice in question.

To scroll through that subset of the reconstruction, select the [Orthoslice] lozenge and go through “Slice Number” in the “Properties” pane.

These combinations of the different plane views of the [**Orthoslice**] and the **Clip tool** help you hide/see particular structures to facilitate scoring. Play around with all three planes and the clip tool to change views as needed.

If you want to hide the slice contents from view and only see the reconstruction, click on the small orange box of the [**Orthoslice**] lozenge. Click it back to visualize slice contents.

If you want to hide more of the bone and the less dense parts of the teeth to improve visualization of the roots for example, you can further adjust the threshold value in the "**Colormap**" to a higher range.

Recording data in an Access database

The Access database “**SVAD_Dental_Morphology_Database**” specifically developed for collecting the dental morphological traits following the protocol presented in this document is accessible for download through the SVAD webpage (<https://www.unr.edu/anthropology/research-and-facilities/subadult-database>).

1. Opening the database

Double click on the Access Database Icon. Once it opens, click on “**Open**” folder to the left, under the red “**Access pane**”, then the “**Browse**” folder and navigate to where the “**SVAD_Dental_Morphology_Database**” file is located on your desktop/machine. Once the file is open, if needed, click on the button “**Enable content**” located in the superior part of the file, just below the toolbar. Next, click on the **Shutter bar** of the “**Navigation**” Pane to the left to open it.

Two sections will appear: first two tables (“**Deciduous**” and “**Permanent**”) that will autopopulate when entering data, and second three forms (“**DataEntry**”, “**Deciduous**” and “**Permanent**”) used to enter data. If the panel is not visible, find the double arrow on the upper left corner, below the “**File**” tab, and click on it to open it.

To start data entry, double-click on the “**DataEntry**” form (the other two forms will not need to be opened or used). The left panel can be minimized by clicking on the double arrow so more space on your screen can be provided for data entry. Once the form is open, two tabs appear:

1. The first tab is called “**Deciduous Dentition**”. It allows the user to enter the medical record/individual number, the anonymized name, the date of data entry, and the name of the observer. This tab is used to record scores of dental morphological traits on the deciduous dentition.
2. The second tab is called “**Permanent Dentition**” and is where permanent dental morphological traits are recorded. The medical record/individual number needs to be reentered here.

2. Scoring with the “DataEntry” form

Once the observer is ready to record the data, these are the steps to follow:

- Open the “**DataEntry**” form by double clicking on it
- Start by entering the information for:
 - Number: anonymized record number/identifier
 - Name (if available): the anonymized name of the individual
 - Date: the date of data entry
 - Observer: your initials
- Then start scoring the deciduous dentition:
 - The upper dentition is above the red line and it is in blue.
 - Teeth are ordered from right to left for the upper dentition, following the dental arcade viewed in the occlusal view and read in a westernized left-to-right way. Upper tooth names appear in blue in the row at the top of that

section. The names of dental morphology traits appear in blue in the first column to the left, while their abbreviations appear in blue in the last column to the right.

- The lower dentition is below the red line and it is in green.
 - The teeth go from left to right for the lower dentition, following the dental arcade when viewed in the occlusal view and read in a westernized left-to-right way. Lower tooth names appear in green in the row at the top of that section. The names of dental morphology traits appear in green in the first column to the left, while their abbreviations appear in green in the last column to the right.
- Each trait for each tooth has a cell with a scrolling bar (click the downward facing arrow in the cell to see it). The list only shows the options available to score that trait. Please use the dental scoring protocol and definitions presented above to choose the best option. Use NA if the tooth is not present and no trait can be scored. Use -1 when the quality of the scans, pathological conditions, medical devices, dental work, or anything else impedes scoring.
- A comment box is provided if notes need to be taken on the quality of the scans, on possible orthodontic work done, or any other remarks the observer might find useful.
- Once the deciduous dentition is done, click on the “**Permanent Dentition**” tab (you might need to scroll upwards in the “**DataEntry**” form to see it below the title “**Dental Morphology – Data Entry**”)
 - Fill in the “**Number**” cell with the anonymized record number/identifier.
 - The traits can now be scored. The organization and color coding for permanent dental traits are the same as for the deciduous dental traits.
- Once all the cells have been filled, the observer must click on the green button “**Add Record**” located on the headline next to the title “**Dental Morphology – Data Entry**”.
- If a mistake has been made and the observer wishes to delete the entire record, it can be deleted in the “**Tables**” section, by right clicking on the left of the row needed to be removed.
- If just one or a few traits need to be deleted:
 - This can be done manually for each trait before clicking on the “**Add Record**” button.
 - Once the record has been added, you can access the tables on the “**Tables**” section and delete/change them directly in the tables themselves, like you would do on an Excel spreadsheet or a Word document.
- After these steps, the form will reappear empty and be ready for the next case to be scored.

Careful!!!

- If the key tab button from your keyboard is used to go from one cell to the next, the observer needs to be careful because most of the time the order follows the tooth. This means that it does not follow the usual left-right and top-bottom order. Instead, it follows the order in which the teeth and traits are scored. Take some time to get used to that order before using the key tab.

- After entering data for a new record, we advise you to open the two tables from the “**Tables**” section and check if the data have autopopulated correctly, especially when the observer is new to using an Access database.

3. Saving the file in Access

Usually, Access saves files automatically before quitting. To be on the safe side, click on the Save button (hard disk icon) located on the left corner of the window regularly.

You will presumably collect data for a certain number of individuals/identifiers in one session and enter them in the Access database after each individual/identifiers you have done.

The files you work with can be named “**projectname_typeofdata_identifier_xxx_yyy**” with xxx the first identifier you entered and yyy the latest identifier you entered in that file.

Every time you reopen the Access database to continue data collection, create a copy of the previous week’s file and work from that new copy. Update the last identifier number/identifier every time you modify it (*i.e.*, “**projectname_typeofdata_identifierxxx_yyy**” to “**projectname_typeofdata_identifier_xxx_zzz**”). That way, data is added on a regular basis and if something happens to your file, you can always revert back to the previous one as a backup.

4. Exporting from Access to Excel/csv

Open the table you would like to export following the first paragraph of step 1. Click on the “**External Data**” tab located on the toolbar. Once there, click on the “**Excel**” option. A new window will open where the destination, name, and format of the file can be selected. Choose .xls for an Excel format. Click the [OK] button. You will then have to open the newly created Excel spreadsheet and go to **File > Save As** and select the .csv format to change the extension of the spreadsheet to .csv. Select the location and name for your new file and click “**Save**”.

Saving the data in a csv/excel spreadsheet and in RDS format

This section only concerns databases in csv/Excel formats and does not apply to Access databases.

Because csv files can be easily corrupted, it is recommended to save each csv file on a regular basis into RDS format.

To do this, open RStudio and run the following code:

```
library(tidyr)
```

```
library(dplyr)
```

```
library(readr)
```

```
library(base)
```

- If you haven't installed these packages before, please do so prior by running the code:
`install.packages("package_name")`

```
#Load old csv file and save it as a RDS file
```

```
File_name <- read_csv("~/path/to/database/File_name.csv")
```

```
write_rds(File_name, "~/path/ to/database/File_name.rds", row.names=FALSE)
```

- The new RDS file will be automatically created in that location (following the path you wrote).

Create a copy of the csv file prior to additional data collection and collect in the new copy.

Update the last identifier number every time you modify it (*i.e.*,

"projectname_typeofdata_identifier_xxx_yyy" to

"projectname_typeofdata_identifier_xxx_zzz"). That way, data is added on a regular/weekly basis and if something happens to the file, you can always revert to the previous one as a backup. You will then save each new weekly csv file as a RDS file so you have backups in RDS formats.

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